

Posulating The Structural Civic Policy Negotiations of Community Higher Education Initiatives in Kerala

Prof K M Vishnu Namboodiri

Assistant Professor and HOD, Department of History, Mar Thoma College, Thiruvalla, Kerala, India

ABSTRACT

The study primarily focuses on the avenue of understanding the relationship that existed between the state machinery and the communities that ventured into the sphere of higher education, the Human factors that determine the fate of communalization of Politics and Rapid advancement of education in the state of Travancore also the dynamic role of private agencies, especially the Christian missionaries who had intensified their educational activities in the state.

- How power structures in the Higher Education Sector of Kerala had its genesis and emerged?
- How were these different groups of the Higher education sector placed during the different regimes, that of Princely State of Travancore, the Travancore-Cochin state, and of the first EMS ministry?
- How can the efficacy and vitality of higher educational reforms and policies till that of 1959 be looked at?

Keywords : Kerala, Higher Education, Communalization, Civic Policies

Specifications Table

Subject area	• <i>Social Sciences</i>
More specific subject area	<i>Research Methodology, Local contextualizing, Interdisciplinary linkage analysis</i>
Method name	<i>Conceptualizing Post-Colonial Post Modern Ergonomic Rereading of the past</i>

Higher Educational Sector had witnessed a significant transformation in the erstwhile Travancore through the last decades of 19th century, into the first half of the twentieth century. The state system had placed in differentiated approaches towards various caste groups and religions when it came to the case of establishment of seats of learning. The pace of change was higher in the decade of power shift from that of a monarchy to a part of democratic, quasi federal setup and finally through the first communist ministry assuming power, initiation of the heavily debated Kerala Education Bill, its legislative negotiations, becoming of an Act, and the removal of the EMS government. The researcher is placing his study in this backdrop.

The study primarily focuses on understanding the relationship that existed between the state machinery and the communities that ventured into the sphere of higher education. Rapid advancement of education in the state of Travancore was to be attributed to the dynamic role of private agencies, especially the Christian missionaries who had intensified their educational activities in the state, but by the beginning of 20th century, caste institutions and various other agencies assumed role in the higher education sector. Politics in the states of Travancore and Cochin was dominated by groups like the church and the Hindu caste organizations especially the NSS and the SNDP. Most of the educational institutions in the private sector gradually came under the control of the Christians and the Hindus. There was an upsurge in the rate of growth of institution in early 1950's i.e. the immediate decade following the independence and the trend continued even after the enactment of the Kerala Education Act. The attempt is in the direction of

observing the pattern of structure of activity that evolved between various entities that involved in the arena of institutionalization of education. The Pro-Caste Hindu policies of the Travancore state especially during the Dewanship of Sir C. P Ramaswami Iyer, and the alienation or the relative absence of Syrian Christian communities and Institutions till the early 1950's find a place in the study. The enquiry into the approximate absence of institutions run by the so called 'Dalit communities' and the marginalized and the weaker sections in the era of "Kerala Renaissance" amuses the researcher. The dynamics of Power balance mechanism in this regard is an area where the researcher wants to dwell deep.

1. JUSTIFICATION FOR THE EFFICACY OF THE STUDY

- Locating the efficacy and vitality of higher educational reforms and policies of the Princely State of Travancore, the Travancore-Cochin state, and of the first EMS ministry, and thereby tracing the development of the pattern of relationships that evolved between the different entities in the higher education system.
- Locating the contextual genesis of community initiatives together with addressing, delineating and locating the space and intervention of the state, societal actors, organized non-state groups and judiciary in the arena of higher education.
- Whole of the policies and reforms in the higher education sector of Kerala including the Kerala Education Act remixed flexibly adjusted for the interest of dominant Hindu caste groups with sub-accommodation of the interest of the Christian and influential Muslim groups, albeit creating the pseudo-impression of inclusiveness towards the marginalized and the "Dalit communities" and when the traditional power centers were affected the various groups united as a force and checked the state machinery and policies from curbing their influence, clout and privileges

2. THE GREEN PATCH FOR RESEARCHERS

- How power structures in the Higher Education Sector of Kerala had its genesis and emerged?
- How were these different groups of the Higher education sector placed during the different regimes, that of Princely State of Travancore,

the Travancore-Cochin state, and of the first EMS ministry?

- How can the efficacy and vitality of higher educational reforms and policies till that of 1959 be looked at?
- What are the methods of analyzing the development of the pattern of relationships that evolved between the different entities in the higher education system?

This study is a qualitative research and shall be interdisciplinary in nature without compromising the essence of historical methodology. As the study is primarily exploratory in nature the researcher also intends to carry out interview with the real players and stakeholders who include officials, academia and public. The study shall be nourished with real time survey as well. The style of writing may hover from theoretical space to descriptive space and vice-versa. The researcher at this juncture feels that a negotiation between Marxian methodology and the feminist angle is an imperative to this study as to address the real issues pertaining to marginalization, alienation and deprivation of basic amenities and resources. Researcher is confident that as the study progress sound theoretical and non-self-contradicting idea and tools can be arrived at.

Additional information:

Umpteen numbers of studies pertaining to the Educational history of Kerala has been carried out by researchers in various fields and discipline, which has indeed contributed in nourishing the outlook and perspective of the researcher in reaching the topic. An array of secondary published works is at disposal which includes, Education and Social Mobility: The Kerala Experience by Sri PT Thomas which focuses on the provision of basic social services, in particular, access to education, as the cardinal building blocks of any human development strategy, the work also signifies a substantial contribution towards the central role of education in social mobility. Social Development and Demographic Changes in South India: Focus on Kerala, By V. Balakrishnan Nair is yet another work which focuses on some unique aspects of community initiatives carried out, which improved the education sector of Kerala, as reflected through data, like that of literacy rate, which in Travancore had been merely 12.4 % and that of cochin being 13.3% in 1901. A few unpublished research thesis's in the field of Economics, Political

Science and Education have also helped the researcher to arrive at the topic that includes Political economy of educational initiatives in Kerala by Dr M S James, Politics of educational management: a case study of the Christian minority in Kerala by Dr Ruble Raj, Educational policy of the Government of India during the British Period by Samuel Raj A, History education at the secondary school level in Kerala state a critical study by Promod VS, among others.

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